

DERIVATIVE SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION OF SPORTS TERMS

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Abstract: As a relatively new branch of linguistics, sports terminology has been arouse more and more linguists' attention. This aricleis dedicated to the research of the derivational characteristics of sports terms.

Key words: sports terms, derivational characteristics, classification

Derivation is the process of creating units of one language on the basis of other units taken as the initial basis, in the simplest case, this is done by expanding the root due to affixation or adding words, in this regard, derivation sometimes is equated with word formation, that is, "the formation of any secondary symbols in a language can be explained by means of units taken as initial, or can be extracted from them by applying certain rules, operations."

The concept of derivation was introduced to designate word-formation practices and was originally equivalent to the term "word-formation". But after the distinction between lexical and syntactic derivation, the concept of derivation began to be applied to the processes of forming language forms outside the word boundary. The expansion of the concept of derivation has led to the study of derivational processes at the text level, and is studied by derivational studies.

The word "derivation" means branching formation, and by this in linguistics it is understood the formation of a specific language unit on the basis of another unit. Currently, derivation is a branch of functional language studies that studies derivation in a broad sense.

In order to reveal the concept of derivation more widely in the big encyclopedic dictionary, it is noted that it should be understood as a term, both word change (inflection) and word-formation are formed subject to certain language rules.

"Derivation is the process of creating words, sentences, grammatical forms of words, word combinations, phraseology, syllables or tacts, and texts, that is, from phonemes to texts, all language units."

We accept the following as a working definition of derivation: derivation is the formation of new words with or without affixation, (in linguistics) word formation.

The concept of derivation was introduced in the middle of the 20th century, one of the outstanding figures of the Prague Linguistic School. After the publication of the scientist's article "Derivatsiya lexicheskaya i derivatsiya semanticheskaya", more attention was paid to the study of issues of derivation in Russian linguistics.

In Uzbek linguistics, serious scientific work on the issues of derivation was carried out, and as a result, about ten dissertations were defended and scientific articles were written.

Whether words are active or inactive from a derivational point of view will certainly depend on their usage levels. Various reasons can be important in this. For example, the presence of synonyms of some words, the obsolescence of others, and the novelty of some are important in determining their derivational status. If a word has synonyms, one of the old and new

words may not have reached the level of derivational activity because of its oldness, and the other because of its newness.

This observation applies both to words in their own layer and to words that have been assimilated. There are such borrowed words that are very active from the point of view of derivational speech. The main reason for this is that "their consumption levels are high".

The word "derivation" means branching, formation, and by this means "formation of a specific language unit on the basis of another unit in linguistics". Currently, derivational problems are being researched in the following three directions in linguistics.

-lexical derivation;

-syntactic derivation;

-semantic derivation.

Lexical derivation deals with grammatical forms of words and problems of word formation.

Syntactic derivation is studied within the framework of questions of formation of word combinations and derivational devices from sentence to microtext.

Semantic derivation deals with the interpretation of language units and derivatives of syntactic devices.

Derivation, of course, takes place on the basis of some material, such a material or raw material is called an operator in derivatology. A derivation event cannot occur without an operator, because the operator is considered the main tool that ensures their emergence in both lexical derivation and syntactic derivation. Therefore, in derivatology, the operator is interpreted as the absolute governing element of the derivation.

Although the concept of lexical derivation has long had its place in the science of linguistics, its interpretation within the framework of monosyllabic words from the point of view of formal-structural analysis requires scientific innovation and is extremely relevant at the current stage of the development of the science of linguistics.

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